

A Fitting Optimization

Alex Avila, Jason Allen, Alex Whittier

April 2017

1 Abstract

Flat sheets are often used to create non-developable surfaces, but there must be some stretching or compression of the sheet during manufacturing to achieve the desired shape [1]. We have developed a method to minimize the strain incurred during manufacturing by optimizing the position of each node of the flat patch. The method is constrained to mimic real-world limitations. We show results of both spherically and non-spherically based shapes with both regular and irregular patches. We discuss what we view as the next steps in non-developable surface optimization, including progression to handling more complicated geometries.

2 Introduction

2.1 Context/Application

Non-developable surfaces, or surfaces with non-zero Gaussian curvature, are used in many applications - in clothing, car bodies, and consumer products such as pop cans. In industry most materials come in flat sheets, which are then stretched and compressed to create non-developable surfaces [1]. The amount of stretching and compression is an important factor in many applications. Some materials will thin and become weak in stretched regions, others work harden and become brittle. Elastic strain energy is also stored in the stretched regions [2]. In general it is advantageous to minimize the amount of stretching and compression that occurs in the transformation from a flat sheet to the non-developable surface.

Non-developable surfaces are often divided up into patches to reduce the strain[1]. The shape of the patch affects how much strain occurs. A patch with long thin sections will require less strain than a rounded patch of equal area. In some cases, such as the modern day sports ball, the shape of the patches are ornamental as well as function. For example, the 2014 World Cup soccer ball was made from six pinwheel shaped patches.

In order to assist in creating new and more intricate shapes, we have set up an optimization to take in any curved surface and create the conjugate flat shape that minimizes the strain [3].

2.2 Literature Review

A lot of work has been done in this area. We will briefly review some of the previous work that has served as a foundation for ours.

In 1991, Shimada presented a method for defining an arbitrary curved surface by a series of vectors formed into triangles. Analysis of the surface is completed through dynamic programming [4].

Parida notes that a major problem in the manufacturing of non-developable surfaces is the cuts and overlaps in the planar surface model. Parida also presents a transformation method that triangulates a 3D surface, and then brings all triangles into the plane of one selected starting triangle by transforming them one at a time [5].

Azariadis divides the optimization of doubly curved surfaces in 3 parts: defining a guide strip and direction of unfolding of the 3D surface, running an unfolding algorithm, and refining the initial pattern [6].

Azariadis et al also developed a real coded genetic algorithm in 2002 for minimizing planar deformation of arbitrary shapes, which uses a non-linear programming method to formulate constraints and then an evolutionary method to minimize the objective function [7].

Wang et al explains that Gaussian curvature is the product of the maximum and minimum normal curvatures at a given point, and has developed an algorithm that determines the optimal cutting path on a doubly curved surface to minimize the stretch when manufactured. Their approach is effective for many complex shapes [8].

Tiwari has developed a mathematically intensive method for determining and minimizing strain fields of Gaussian curved surfaces [9].

And finally, Yu et al worked on flattening 3D shapes by looking at the strain, but in a different way from what we have done. They looked at a solution where only stretching is required from the 3D shape to the planar. They also provided many mathematical equations and methods to optimize the layout. They provided many mathematical models that can be used for working with doubly shaped objects [10].

3 Methodology

3.1 Problem Set Up

We map a non-developable three-dimensional (3D) shape to a two-dimensional (2D) plane. The 3D shape is discretized into a triangular mesh in CAD software. We optimize the nodes of the corresponding mesh (patch) in the 2D plane, minimizing the maximum strain that results from stretching the nodes from the 2D plane to their location on the 3D surface. The node positions were optimized using the "active-set" method of Matlab's `fmincon` function.

3.2 Objective Function

Strain ϵ_I of each line i is given by

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{\|\vec{L}_{3D_i}\| - \|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|}{\|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|} = \frac{\|\vec{L}_{3D_i}\|}{\|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|} - 1 \quad (1)$$

ϵ_I can also be represented by the equation:

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{L_3}{\sqrt{(x_j - x_k)^2 + (x_l - x_m)^2}} - 1 \quad (2)$$

L_3 is constant so when taking the partial derivatives, where x_j is the variable being changed, gives:

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{L_3(x_k - x_j)}{((x_j - x_k)^2 + (x_l - x_m)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - 1 \quad (3)$$

Where $\|\vec{L}_{3D_i}\|$ is the length of the line i of the curved surface and $\|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|$ is the length of the corresponding line i in the 2D space.

The objective obj is the 2-norm of the strain

$$obj = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i^2} \quad (4)$$

The partial gradient of obj is

$$\frac{\partial obj}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \epsilon_i}{\partial x_j} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i^2}} \quad (5)$$

where x_j is design variable j .

3.3 Constraints

3.3.1 Crossover Constraint

A critical constraint for optimizing 2D patch shape was ensuring that none of the nodes move so much from their original position that they cross over triangle boundaries and create impossible shapes. To meet this requirement, we developed a method that checks to see if the z-component of the cross products of each pair of vectors in each triangle are negative. If any cross products are positive, the constraint is violated. Figure 1 shows the optimal shapes for a simple example with and without the constraint 2. The pattern on the right would not be physically possible.

Figure 1: This is a comparison of the optimal shapes calculated with and without the crossover constraint.

c_2 is given by

$$c_{2i} = \vec{v}_i \times \vec{u}_i \quad (6)$$

Where \vec{v} and \vec{u} are vectors that make up two sides of a triangle in the mesh.

The gradient of c_2 is given by

$$\frac{\partial c_{2i}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \vec{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \times \vec{v}_i + \frac{\partial \vec{v}_i}{\partial x_j} \times \vec{u}_i \quad (7)$$

3.3.2 No Compression Constraint

One of the most important constraints for our project was to make sure that the material only stretches (no contraction) as it goes from the 2D patch to the 3D shape. This better mimics the behavior of a patch that is stretched around a ball in the real-world. This constraint was added as an inequality constraint in which the 2D line length must be equal to or less than corresponding 3D line length.

c_1 is given by

$$c_{1i} = \|L_{2D_i}\| - \|L_{3D_i}\| \quad (8)$$

Figure 2: This is a comparison of the strain between the patterns with the no compression constraint applied (left) and not applied (right).

Where $\|\vec{L}_{3D_i}\|$ is the length of the line i of the curved surface and $\|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|$ is the length of the corresponding line i in the 2D space.

We included the gradient of this constraint in order to decrease the number of function calls. This constraint was done by calculating the partial derivatives based on the coordinates for the 2D lines. Since the length and coordinates of the 3D line are constant, the gradients for the 3D line are all zero. We took the equation to calculate the length of the 2D line using the basic line length equation and created partial derivatives based on the x_1 , x_2 , y_1 , and y_2 coordinates. These were done by taking the change in position divided by the length. These were put into the gradient matrix along with zeros for the partial derivative values for the 3D line.

The partial gradient of c_1 is given by

$$\frac{\partial c_{1i}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \vec{L}_{2D_i}}{\partial x_j} \frac{L_{2D_i}}{\|\vec{L}_{2D_i}\|} \quad (9)$$

The no compression constraint affected patterns with long skinny members much less than patterns with short wide members. For example, the nodes of the circular shaped patch in Fig. 3 are more interconnected, meaning that the strain of each line is more dependent than the skinny pattern in Fig. 2. This makes the pattern tend to want to compress in inner regions and expand in extremity regions. Table 1 shows the comparison of the change in the strain for both shapes in Fig. 3.

3.4 Selecting Initial Conditions

Providing a good first guess from which the optimizer can begin iterations makes the optimization as efficient and reliable as possible. We wanted to develop a function for determining initial conditions that would be both simple and effective. Since our objective function takes a 3D surface and maps it into a 2D plane, our initial guess needed to provide 2D information.

Total Strain	Circle	Skinny
Applied	5.439e9	1.338e9
Not Applied	1.983e9	0.920e9
Difference (%)	64	31

Table 1: The decrease in strain when the no compression constrain is relaxed for the circle and skinny patches shown in Fig 3.

Figure 3: This is a comparison of the optimal shapes calculated with and without the no compression constraint. Although both patches were originally from a spherical surface the difference is greater for the circular patch because the nodes are more interconnected.

The first, and our current, method for determining the initial conditions is to simply keep the x and y components of the (x,y,z) spatial location of each node from the STL file while discarding the z component. This very easily creates a planar set of initial points. However, this method is only useful for shapes with little curvature. As the objective patch shape approaches a full hemisphere, several of the initial points are mapped to almost overlaying spots, and once a patch has more curvature than a half sphere, the method becomes impossible due to repeated and overlapping positions of nodes.

We think a better approach will be to apply the same principle of 3D to 2D mapping, but to do so one triangle at a time, instead of the entire patch. The idea is to look at each triangle from a frame of reference perpendicular to its plane. We can then calculate the distance between each node of the triangle, and pair them up with the nodes of the surrounding triangles. Doing this iteratively for every triangle will create a planar model that can serve as an initial guess for shapes with hemispherical or greater curvature.

3.5 Creating Patches

To create our 3D shapes, we designed them in Solidworks and then exported them as STL files. We found a Matlab package online used to read in STL files called “stlread.m”. There is an additional file called “patchslim.m” used to identify and remove duplicate vertices. These files read in the triangular faces from the STL files and then return the vertices and faces separately. They also return the face normal vectors which we used in some of our constraints.

4 Results

Although there remains much to be explored in the minimization of stretching for non-developable surfaces, we are pleased with the results we have attained so far.

As we worked with the harder 3D shapes, we noticed that the problem would stop because the expected change in the objective function and the constraint function were both less than the default $1e-6$. In order to see if this was a good tolerance size, we changed it several times to see how this affected our solution. We first started by changing the tolerances for both to $1e-10$. The optimized shapes had no noticeable visual difference. The first-order optimalities were relatively close ($9.71e-05$ compared to $9.22e-07$). The total function calls however only increased by 30 for the given test case of intermediate difficulty, which is not significant. Next the tolerances were changed to $1e-15$. This time had a hard time converging because we realized it was getting close to machine epsilon. The function value would decrease and then increase, as well as the first-order optimality. It eventually appeared to just stagnate.

From these tolerance tests, we decided to use tolerances of $1e-10$ because it improves our first order optimality by two orders of magnitude with only a few extra function calls. This will need to be checked again on harder test cases to see if it still worth it in terms of increased number of function calls. We learned also that we cannot use too small of a tolerance otherwise it will have a hard time converging.

Figure 4: A non-spherical doubly curved shape and its conjugate patch.

4.1 Physical Test

We looked at testing our optimization on a physical example with the help of a manufacturing graduate student with access to a hydraulic press. We began by creating a 3D model of a shape based off the shape of the ball that was going to be used to deform our physical patch. We then used our program to make a planar version of that shape (see Fig. 5). and cut the design out of steel using a water jet cutter (see Fig. 6). We later cut a version out of aluminum because of some problems with the steel patch.

The shape was tested on a hydraulic press located on campus. The press works by pushing a ball up into a socket causing the part to wrap around the sphere. Because of the size of our part, we put a sheet of metal on top of it to hold it in place while it was being tested. We originally tested the steel patch, but we could not get it to deform enough because the materials used to hold it down fractured too early causing

Figure 5: Optimized layout for physical patch to be tested.

Figure 6: Planar physical prototype cut out of steel on the water jet cutter.

the hydraulic press to stop. To fix this, we cut the same shape out of aluminum and reran the test. The aluminum worked much better, actually deforming around the sphere (see Fig. 8).

Figure 7: Hydraulic press used to test our physical patches.

After testing the part, we went to scan it to see how it compared to the original 3D model that it was based off of. The scanner we went to use scans physical parts and creates a 3D model of them. Unfortunately, we were unable to use the scanner because the software license key was expired. We would like to do it in the future when the license has been renewed. Because we were unable to use the scanner, we used a 3D printer to create the original shape for us to compare our physical patch to. We were pleased with the results. The aluminum physical patch was very close in curvature and deflection to the 3D printed version. There were some discrepancies which we think can be attributed to springback in the aluminum patch.

5 Conclusions

Although there remains improvement work to be done, our program is feasible. It successfully takes 3D shapes and outputs an optimized 2D pattern with minimal strain. The program runs quickly and is user friendly, thus making it attractive as a tool for many projects. The user only needs to provide an STL file of the patch to be optimized, and the program automatically generates the initial conditions and works through all the optimization metrics without any further input.

5.1 Future Work

Moving forward, there are several things that could be done to further enhance our project. Primarily, improving the technique for generating an initial guess would allow for optimization of more complex shapes. We believe that mapping each node to the plane instead of simply eliminating the z-component will be an effective approach. Also, creating a method for ensuring that the triangles on the surface are all similar in size will help the optimizer run smoothly and efficiently. Finally, developing a method to integrate a stiffness

Figure 8: Physical patch after being formed in a hydraulic press (left) compared with a 3D print of the original CAD model (right).

matrix method in the approach will allow for material-specific analysis, thus providing more accurate results. It would also be beneficial to test our physical patches with the 3D scanner when possible.

References

- [1] B. Hinds, J. McCartney, and G. Woods, “Pattern development for 3d surfaces,” *Computer-aided design*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 583–592, 1991.
- [2] C. C. Wang, “Towards flattenable mesh surfaces,” *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 109–122, 2008.
- [3] E. D. Demaine, M. L. Demaine, J. Iacono, and S. Langerman, “Wrapping spheres with flat paper,” *Computational geometry*, vol. 42, no. 8, pp. 748–757, 2009.
- [4] T. Shimada and Y. Tada, “Approximate transformation of an arbitrary curved surface into a plane using dynamic programming,” *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 153–159, 1991.
- [5] L. Parida and S. Mudur, “Constraint-satisfying planar development of complex surfaces,” *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 225–232, 1993.
- [6] P. Azariadis and N. Aspragathos, “Design of plane developments of doubly curved surfaces,” *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 675–685, 1997.
- [7] P. N. Azariadis, A. C. Nearchou, and N. A. Aspragathos, “An evolutionary algorithm for generating planar developments of arbitrarily curved surfaces,” *Computers in Industry*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 357–368, 2002.
- [8] C. C. Wang, Y. Wang, K. Tang, and M. M. Yuen, “Reduce the stretch in surface flattening by finding cutting paths to the surface boundary,” *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 665–677, 2004.
- [9] A. Tiwari, A. da Chatterjee, V. K. Pathak, and S. G. Dhande, “Strain field in doubly curved surface,” *Int J Eng Modell*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2007.
- [10] G. Yu, N. M. Patrikalakis, and T. Maekawa, “Optimal development of doubly curved surfaces,” *Computer Aided Geometric Design*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 545–577, 2000, ISSN: 0167-8396. DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8396\(00\)00017-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8396(00)00017-0). [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167839600000170>.